

**A DEVELOPMENT OF STRESS MANAGEMENT PROGRAM FOR THE
ADOLESCENTS AND STUDY OF ITS EFFECTIVENESS**

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Abstract

A stress is a major concern of modern society. The medical field also affirms that stress is a major factor which contributes to the psychosomatic diseases. It is a fact of worry that adolescents are also facing stress; moreover, in the school curricula there is no any program which can help them to face stress positively. Because of stress, the problem of students' suicides is becoming crucial. In the present study, the researcher developed a program for the management of stress of adolescents. The study habits, self-esteem, and assertiveness these parameters of a stress are considered while developing a program. The impact of the program is studied and analysis is presented in the present paper.

Introduction-

A stress, tension, anxiety have become very common words today. It is said that stress is a silent killer. If we do not pay attention towards our stress its intensity may be increased. Continuous stress can convert in psychological disorders. It is very important for everyone to be happy and enjoy the life. All the situations may not be favorable but we must have confidence and belief that every situation we can overcome. People from all the age groups faces some or the other type of stress. It is a severe situation that school children are also facing stress. The pressure of the studies, parental expectations, cut throat competitions are very important factors for generating stress among children. Suicide cases of adolescents are a burning issue nowadays. It is also a fact that in our school curriculum we don't have any mechanism or program which can guide students to manage stress. It an urgent need of an hour to develop a program which can help the school children to manage stress positively.

Need of the Study –

The present study mainly focuses on the adolescent stress on secondary level students. This study has strengths to bring change for the management of stress at various levels of education. Moreover, on the basis of factors related to the stress(Self-Esteem, Study Habits, Assertiveness) Stress Management Program developed by the researcher provides practical techniques to the students which enable them to understand stress & the various programs under it will help students to tackle stress positively.

Stress is a natural part of life that can either help us learn and grow, or can cause us significant problems .Severe stress releases powerful Neuro-chemicals and hormones that prepare us for action (to fight or flee). If we don't take action, the stress response can lead to health

problems. Prolonged, uninterrupted, unexpected, and unmanageable stresses are the most damaging types of stress.

Statement of the Problem –

A Development of Stress Management Program for the Adolescent students studying in a Secondary school in Mumbai City and Study of its Effectiveness.

Operational Definitions –

The researcher had used some words with their specific meanings restricted for the present study. These operational definitions of such words are given below

1) Adolescents -

Students of 9th standard (13 to 15 age group) studying in the English Medium schools at greater Mumbai.

2) Secondary Schools –

Secondary English medium schools in greater Mumbai, affiliated to the Higher Secondary Board of Maharashtra State.

3) Stress Management – stress management refers to changing any aspect of the stress related to self-esteem, study habits, and assertiveness.

4) Stress Management Program –

The program developed by the researcher for the stress management of adolescents, which will improve the self-esteem, study habits.

5) Stress -

For the present study Stress emerged from the following factors are considered as stress

- a) Stress caused by poor self- esteem
- b) Stress caused by poor study habits
- c) Stress caused by Non-Assertiveness (peer pressure)
- 7) Self-Esteem- Self respect and self- worth as perceived by the adolescents.
- 8) Study-Habits- Pattern of study and style of learning activities to improve academic performance and understanding of the subject of an individual.
- 9) **Assertiveness-** For the study, Assertiveness was considered as an important factor for the adolescents to keep away from peer –pressure.

Scope of the Study –

- 1) In the present research, a level of stress among adolescent boys and girls of English medium secondary schools is studied. (IX standard is selected for the study).
- 2) The researcher has developed a program for the stress management of secondary school students. Self-esteem, study habits, assertiveness these factors are considered while developing the stress management program.
- 3) Post -treatment results of the experimental and controlled group are analyzed on the basis of Level of stress, Self-esteem, study habits, assertiveness, and gender.

Objectives of the Study:

Following objectives were formulated for the study.

- 1) To find out the level of stress among adolescent students.
- 2) To develop a stress management program for adolescents to face stress positively.

- 3) To implement developed stress management program.
- 4) To study the effectiveness of ‘Stress Management Program’ on the adolescents in relation to -
 - a) Study habits
 - b) Self-esteem
 - c) Assertiveness

Hypothesis –

It was observed that previous researches in the area of stress show that adolescents are in need of understanding various stress management techniques. Hence the hypotheses for this study were formulated as follows:

- 1) There is no significant difference in the mean scores of the stress level of adolescents of experimental & control group before and after implementing stress management program.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the mean scores of study habits of adolescents before and after implementing stress management program.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the mean scores of self- esteem of adolescents before and after implementing intervention program.
- 4) There is no significant difference in the mean scores of assertiveness of adolescents before and after implementing intervention program.

Tools –

For the present study following tools were used.

- 1) Revised Comprehensive Anxiety Test (CA-Test) (2006)– This test is developed by Dr. Bharadwaj ,Dr.H.Sharma & Dr.M.Bhargava .This is a standardized test used to study the stress. This test is applicable for all the age groups
- 2) Children’s Self-Concept Test (CSCS) - For measuring the self concept of adolescents. By S.P. Ahluwalia, this is standardized test, face validity; concurrent validity and factorial validity have been established.
- 3) Study Habits Inventory – for understanding the study habits of the adolescents test by Dr.T.Pradeep Kumar, APH Publication Corporation.
- 4) Assertiveness Scale- To measure the assertiveness of the adolescents, Assertiveness Scale was developed by the researcher.
- 5) ‘Stress management Program.

Research Design –

In the present research to assess the effectiveness of intervention i.e. “Stress Management Program” Two group pre-test, a post-test design of experimental research is used. The comparison is studied between experimental and control group. In the selected English medium school Comprehensive anxiety Test was given to the students from four division of 9th standard. On the basis of the results of the test according to the level of stress two groups were formed i.e. experimental group (exposed to intervention) and control group (non-intervention group). In both, the groups were consisting 20 boys and 20 girls.

'Stress Management Program was developed' The objective of this program was to measure the change in the dependent variable i.e. Self- esteem, assertiveness and Study habits of the adolescents.

- a) To study the effect of developed program experimental research methodology was used.
- b) As far as implementation of the developed program is concerned two equivalent groups were formed in which one was controlled and another was experimental group. Equivalent groups were formed as per the scores of comprehensive anxiety Test.

Sampling

- 1) For the experimental study, one English medium school from grater Mumbai was selected with purposive sampling.
- 2) From selected school, two divisions of 9th standard are selected with random sampling method.
- 3) Forty students were selected on the basis of Comprehensive Anxiety Test scores.
- 4) Two equivalent groups were formed viz. controlled and experimental.

	Experimental	Control	Total
	40	40	80
Boys	20	20	40
Girls	20	20	40

Procedure _

- Comprehensive Anxiety Test administered to study the level of stress among adolescent students of IX standard.
- On the basis of the results of Comprehensive Anxiety Test two equivalent groups were formed.
- Among the students who have a high, moderate and low level of stress only students who have the moderate level of stress were selected to form groups.
- To study the self-esteem, study habits, and assertiveness, tests and inventories were administered.
- The researcher has developed the stress management program.
- The developed program was validated by the experts in the field of Psychology and education.
- Stress Management Program was implemented on the experimental group.
- After implementing the program as a post –test was administered to analyze the change in stress level, Self -Concept, Study habits and assertiveness.

Data Analysis & Interpretation-

For the present study, the researcher has used t-test, a parametric statistical techniques to test the null hypothesis.

A level of Significance- For the present study, the researcher has used 0.05 level of significance for rejecting or accepting the null hypothesis.

Testing of hypothesis-

Hypothesis: 1

Hypothesis 1 states that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the stress level of adolescents of experimental & control group before and after implementing stress management program.

Technique used – paired t test

Variable – Level of Stress

Groups – Experimental

Table: 2 Pre-test and Post-test Comparison of Mean scores of Experimental group.

Group	N	Pre-Test		Pot-test		t value	CR
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Experimental	40	63.87	4.37	51.22	4.31	3.09	2.02

From the table:2 ,‘t’ test analysis indicated that adolescents of The experimental group (N=40) differ significantly in their level of stress between the pre-test and the post-test at 0.05 level of significance. The level of stress the post-test is significantly lower than that of the pre-test. The mean score of the post-test (M=51.22) is lower than that of the pre-test (M=63.87) of the Experimental group. Also, it was found that the gain score of the experimental group was greater than that of control group between the pre-test and post-test. As far as a standard deviation of post-test and pre-test of the experimental group is concerned there was a significant difference was noted. (S.D. of post- test 4.62 and S.D. of pre-test 4.31). t- Value obtained for the experimental group is 3.09 is greater; the value is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. This is proved that the intervention strategies regarding management of stress have helped the adolescents to reduce stress. As far as adolescents of the control group are concerned they do not differ significantly in their level of stress in the pre-test and post-test scores.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of study habits of adolescents in the control group and experimental group before and after implementing stress management program.

Technique used – paired t test

Variable – Study Habits

Group – Experimental

Table:.3 Analysis of Effectiveness of intervention program for Study Habits

Experimental Group	N	Pre-test		Post Test		t	CR
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Study Habits	40	67.45	7.89	85.35	7.25	6.36	2.09

From the table:3 ‘t’ test analysis indicated that adolescents of the experimental group (N=40) differ significantly in their study habits in the post-test at 0.05 level. When the mean scores of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group are compared, the post – test mean score of the experimental group (M=85.35) is greater than that of the pre-test mean score of the experimental group (M=67.45). As far as the standard deviation of these two groups is concerned, there is a significant difference (S.D. of pre-test is 7.89 and S.D of post –test is 7.25). The t- value obtained for pre-test and post-test of the experimental group is 6.36 which is greater than critical value 2.02. Hence it is inferred that the various strategies introduced for improving study habits helped the adolescents to improve their study habits. Hence the enhancement in study habits proved that the strategy was effective and the hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of self -esteem of adolescents before and after implementing stress management Program.

Technique used – paired t test

Variable – Self-esteem

Group – Experimental

Table: 4 Analysis of Effectiveness of intervention program for Self-Esteem

Experimental Group	Pre-test		Post Test		t	CR
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Self-Esteem	58.17	4.98	70.05	4.05	6.98	2.02

From the table: 4 ‘t’ test analysis indicated that adolescents of the experimental group (N=40) differ significantly in their self -esteem in the post-test at 0.05 level. When the mean scores of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group are compared, there is a significant difference in the gain scores of the group. Therefore, it is inferred that intervention strategies for self-esteem proved effective for developing self-esteem. The post – test mean score of the experimental group (M=70.05) is greater than that of the post-test mean score of the control group (M=57) As far as the standard deviation of the group is concerned, there is a significant difference pre-test (S.D. of Experimental .group is 4.98 and S.D of post-test is 4.05). The t-value obtained for the experimental group is 6.98 is greater than the critical value. Hence it is inferred that the Intervention strategy opens up possibilities to help more in enhancing self- esteem. The mean scores of the experimental group are greater than that of the mean scores of the Control group which indicated that self-esteem Intervention strategies helped the adolescents to improve their self-esteem. Hence it helped the adolescents to manage stress positively.

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of assertiveness of adolescents before and after implementing stress management program.

Technique used – paired t test

Variable – Self-esteem

Group – Experimental

Tabel: 5

Experimental Group Assertiveness	Pre-test		Post Test		t	CR
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
	59.45	3.25	69.55	1.98		

From the table: 5, ‘t’ test analysis indicated Adolescents in the experimental group (N=40) differ significantly in their assertiveness between the pre-test and the post-test at 0.05 level. The mean score of the post-test (M=69.55) is greater than the mean score of the pre-test. (M=59.45). This indicates the Experimental group of adolescents as far as the standard deviation of the post-test (S.D=1.98) and the pretest (S.D = 3.25) scores of the Experimental group of adolescents are concerned; there is a significant difference in their assertiveness. This, in turn, helped to enhance firmness in behavior. From the above statistics, it can be seen that Experimental group of adolescents has enhanced assertiveness, as they have the significant difference in their scores towards assertive behavior in the post – test than the pre-test. The t-value obtained for the experimental group is 9.77 is higher than the critical value 2.02. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is proved that the strategy was found effective to enhance assertiveness among adolescents.

Findings

The major findings of the study are discussed below:

- There is a significant difference in the mean scores for the variable Stress of experimental group before and after implementing intervention program. This clearly indicates an impact of the stress management strategies. The tremendous decrease in the Mean score in post-test scores of the experimental group in lowering the level of stress shows the strategy proved effective. It can be said that adolescents do differ in their level of stress because of the treatment to the experimental group and it means that Stress Management Program implemented by the researcher is effective on experimental group.
- There was no significant difference observed for the variable stress of control group. The level of stress is slightly increased for the control group than the pre-test.
- There is a significant difference observed for the variable study Habits. Adolescents of the experimental group differ significantly in their study habits in the post-test. Hence it is inferred that the various strategies introduced for improving study habits helped the adolescents to improve their study habits. Hence the improvement in study habits proved that the strategy was effective and the hypothesis is rejected.
- There was no improvement observed for the variable study habits in the post-test of the control group.

- Adolescents of the experimental group differ significantly in their self- esteem in the post-test. Therefore, it is inferred that intervention strategies for self-esteem proved effective for developing self-esteem for the experimental group of adolescents.
- There was no improvement observed for the variable study habits in the post-test of the control group.
- There was no improvement observed for the variable self-esteem in the post-test of the control group.
- The experimental group of adolescents differs significantly for the scores of assertiveness in the post-test. This, in turn, helped to enhance firmness in behavior. The statistical analysis has proved that Experimental group of adolescents has enhanced assertiveness.
- There was no improvement observed for the variable assertiveness in the post-test of the control group.

Conclusion

The findings of the research hope to serve valuable insights for the management of stress among adolescents. The program developed by the researcher will be helpful for assist school students, college teachers and all stakeholders of education for the betterment of education.

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